

CHIKITSA SUTRA AND MANAGEMENT OF ASTHI AND MAJJAVAHA SROTAS: AN AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVESDr. Neeraj Kanungo^{1*}, Zahida Nagori²

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According to the principles of Ayurveda, *Majja Dhatu* refers to a type of *Dhatu* that is found in the bones. When there is an increased level of *Vata Dosha* the degeneration of *Majja Dhatu* occurs, this is referred to as *Asthi Kshaya*. Clinical manifestations of *Majja Kshaya* may include the development of *Asthi Saushirya* and *Asthi Daurbalya* as well as many modern "diseases" associated with these disorders. The loss of bone tissue due to *Asthi Kshaya* occurs due to the lack of nutrients necessary to nourish the bones. The *Chikitsa Sutra* focuses on bringing the functions of *Srota* back to normal *via* a systematic treatment strategy. The first stage uses *Panchakarma* methods to open up blocked channels and cleanse them. The second stage involves using an individual's personal diet to restore balance to the channels through sweet and bitter foods for *Majjavaha Srotas* and oily foods for *Asthivaha Srotas*. The third stage uses medications and therapeutic treatment to manage the imbalances between the primary *Doshas*. This article discusses vitiation of *Asthi* and *Majjavaha Srotas* and their management through Ayurvedic perspectives.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda, Asthi, Majja, Srotas, Chikitsa Sutra.***INTRODUCTION**

Asthi-Majja DhatuKshaya can begin with sensation of pain and weakness in the bones. Once this has progressed, other symptoms may include severe pain in the bones and teeth through to structural deformities in the skeleton. A common feature includes generalized weakness, fatigue and gradual loss of muscle mass.^[1, 2]

Aggravated *Vaata Dosha* with *Vyaana Vaata* plays predominant role in *Asthi-Majja Dhatu Kshaya's*. The main *Samprapti Ghataka* influencing this condition includes the *Asthi-Majja Dhatu*, the *Asthivah* and *Majjavah Sroto* and the *Srotodosh*. Some common sites of clinical manifestation include *Kaati, Janu, Shroni, Manibandha* and *Prishthavanik*. The cause of *Asthi-kshaya* ultimately due to increased *Vaata* disorders as a result of *Sharada Vaata* aggravated through *Srotodosh*.

Thus an impaired state of the *Medovaha, Asthivaha* and *Majjavaha Sroto* leads to depletion of the *Asthidhatu*.^[2-4]

Causes of Vitiation

There are many reasons for the vitiation of the *Majjavaha Srotas*, such as *Prapedana, Abhighata, Utpeshana, Abhishyandi* and *Viruddha Anna Sevana*, as well as excessive engagement in *Vyayama* and *Maithuna*, may all lead to an imbalance within these channels. *Bhrama, Murchha* and *Sthoola Malapravritti* are clinical manifestations of *Majjavaha Srotas Dushti*.

Ayurvedic Management of Asthi–Majja Dhatukshaya

Ayurvedic protocols focus on building and maintaining *Asthi* and *Majja dhatu*s while balancing *Vaat dosha*. Dietary guidelines includes intake of *ghee*, milk, and supportive herbal supplements for strength, including *Guduchi* and *Shatavari*, along with sufficient calcium,

protein, and Vitamin D. *Rasayana* herbs such as *Ashwagandha*, *Hadjod* and *Bala* are known for their rejuvenating properties for bones. Additionally, *Yoga* and *Abhyanga* are recommended within Ayurveda to balance *Vata dosha*, improve circulation, and support joint stability. *Panchakarma* treatments, especially *Basti*, have long been considered a cornerstone of preventing and restoring *Asthi Kshaya*. Following therapeutic measures may be recommended for managing specific conditions.^[4-6]

- ✚ *Vatahara* oils for *Bahya* and *Abhyantara Snehan*
- ✚ *Kayaseka* for oleation and sudation
- ✚ *Asthivaha Srotodushti Chikitsa* using *Tikta-dravya* processed *Ksheera* and *Ghritha*
- ✚ *Upanaha* and *Agnikarma* for localized *Vata* disorders
- ✚ *Bandhana* and *Unmardana* for musculoskeletal support
- ✚ *Rasayana* therapy, including *Guggulu Rasayana*, *Brahma Rasayana* and *Chyavanaprasha* helps to promote quality of *Dhatu*s.

Ayurveda's approach to correct the causes of the weakening of *Asthivaha Srotas* is through understanding and reducing the causes of *Vata* aggravation. The Ayurvedic approach to the prevention of bone injuries is achieved through the utilization of *Panchakarma*, especially *Tikta Kshira Basti* in conjunction with other types of *Vasti* therapies involving medicated ghee and milk to directly calm excess *Vata* and nourish *Asthi Dhatu*. Foods and dietary products that contain fats, ghee, milk, and a predominance of the *Madhura* and *satvik* properties should be consumed to normalize *Asthivaha Srotas*.^[5-7] The treatment for *Majjavaha Srotas* is based on some main objectives as mentioned in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Major approaches of treating vitiation of Majjavaha Srotas.

The *Majjavaha* are channels in the body that feed and support the *Majja Dhatu*. The *Mulasthanas* of the *Majjavaha Srotas* are the *Asthi* and *Sandhi*, since *Majja* is formed in and stored in the cavities of long bones and is functionally protected and affected by the structural properties of the joints. Bone marrow is located within the medullary cavity of the bone. *Majjavaha Srotas* provide nourishment to both the marrow and all nerve tissue, thereby aiding in the sensory, motor, coordination, consciousness, and communication between the body and the mind. As part of the dietary guidelines, *Madhura* and *Tikta Rasa* are particularly effective in promoting *Majja Dhatu* and calming *Vata* without further aggravating *Kapha*. *Shodhana* therapies used in *Panchakarma* such as *Vamana* and *Virechana* should be performed according to *Ritu* and the strength of the individual and therefore are effective in cleaning the *Srotas* and improving nutrition to the tissues.^[8-10] **Table 1** depicted some drugs which are considered useful for managing *Asthivaha* and *Majjavaha Srotas Dushti*.

Table 1: Some common drugs recommended for Asthivaha and Majjavaha Srotas Dushti.

Srotas	Drug	Karma
Asthivaha Srotas	<i>Asthishrinkhala</i>	<i>Asthi-poshaka</i>
	<i>Laksha</i>	Strengthens <i>Asthi</i>
	<i>Arjuna</i>	Supports bone & connective tissue
	<i>Ashwagandha</i>	<i>Balya</i> , <i>Brimhana</i> , <i>Vata-shamaka</i>
	<i>Shatavari</i>	<i>Dhatu-poshana</i> , <i>Asthi-balya</i>
	<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Rasayana</i> , anti-inflammatory
	<i>Guggulu</i>	Reduces degeneration, anti-inflammatory
	<i>Praval Bhasma</i>	<i>Asthi-balya</i> , calcium support
	<i>Mukta Bhasma</i>	Strengthens bones, <i>Pittashamaka</i>
	<i>Godanti Bhasma</i>	Useful in <i>Asthi</i> disorders
	<i>Kukkutandatvak Bhasma</i>	Promotes bone density
Majjavaha Srotas	<i>Ashwagandha</i>	<i>Majja-varadhaka</i> , nervine tonic
	<i>Bala</i>	<i>Balya</i> , nerve & marrow strength
	<i>Kapikacchu</i>	Neuroprotective, <i>Majja-poshaka</i>
	<i>Brahmi</i>	<i>Medhya</i> , CNS support
	<i>Shankhapushpi</i>	<i>Medhya</i> , nervine rejuvenator
	<i>Vacha</i>	Stimulates nerve function (low dose)
	<i>Jyotishmati</i>	Enhances nerve conduction
	<i>Brahmi Ghritha</i>	<i>Majja-poshana</i> , <i>Medhya</i>
	<i>Mahakalyanaka Ghritha</i>	CNS tonic, <i>Rasayana</i>
	<i>Ashwagandha Ghritha</i>	<i>Brimhana</i> , <i>Majja-balya</i>

CONCLUSION

In Ayurvedic medicine, *Asthi Dhatu* is formed through the metabolic process of *Ahara Rasa* and *Meda Dhatu*. The *Asthivaha srotas* and *Asthyagni* provide the basis for nourishing & maintaining bone health. The treatment of *Asthi-Majja Dhatukshaya* with Ayurveda targets the whole person and focuses on nourishing both the *Asthi* and *Majja Dhatu*s and calming down any excessive *Vata*. Treatment methods include proper *Ahara-Vihara*, *Rasayana* therapy, *Panchakarma* and also supportive methods such as *Abhyanga* and *Yoga* will address the causes and effects of *Dhatu Kshaya*. The combined approach of treatment by Ayurveda restores the *Srotas*, improves tissue quality, and stops the further deterioration of the musculoskeletal & nervous system.

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